

**PRINT VS. SOCIAL MEDIA ADVERTISEMENT: ITS EFFECTIVNESS
AS MARKETING STRATEGY OF CVCITC**

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ABSTRACT

This study focused on the print vs. social media advertisement and its effectiveness as marketing strategy. The aims of this study are determined which advertising medium, print or social media is easier for students to use and where they can accelerate their learning based on their preferences. It sought to determine (1) the level of effectiveness on the use of print initiatives of CVCITC in terms of (a) persuasion (b) attraction (c) self-involvement (2) the level of effectiveness on the use of social media advertisement of CVCITC in terms of (a) persuasion (b) acceptability (c) self-involvement (3) the level of effectiveness on the use of print media initiatives to the level of effectiveness on the use of social media advertisement of CVCITC. This study was conducted last October 2023 to April 2024. The respondents of the study were Senior High School Students enrolled in Cagayan Valley Computer and Information Technology College. Using Slovin's formula with a 5% margin of error, there were 249 respondents whose involvement was elicited for this study. The researcher utilized the surveyed questionnaires in assessing the effectiveness of print vs. social media advertisement as marketing strategy. Research instrument underwent validation and was subjected to data analysis procedures. This study discusses the effectiveness of print vs. social media as a strategic tool. As a result, it can also help in building your organization strong enough to make your marketing effective.

INTRODUCTION

The popularity of social media has increased in the internet sphere. Nowadays, social media platforms are used by the majority of enterprises, including educational institutions,

colleges, and universities, as part of their marketing strategy (Chanthinok, K., Ussahawanitchakit, P., & Jhundra-Indra, P., 2015). The use of social media to promote events or items to potential clients online is known as social media marketing (SMM) (Ibrahim, B., & Aljarah, A., 2018).

Additionally, in addition to facilitating activities that raise brand awareness, social media marketing effectively promotes communications between marketers and consumers (Hafez M., 2021). As the number of social media marketing platforms and active users has grown over time, social media marketing has become one of the most significant uses of the Internet. Businesses have shifted their marketing efforts to social media platforms at an equally rapid pace (Aichner, T., Grünfelder, M., Maurer, O., & Jegeni, D., 2021). As a result, social media is currently one of the greatest ways for a business to connect with potential buyers. By connecting with consumers on a deeper level, these new media gain their trust (Sajid S.I., 2016).

Conversely, print advertising is a marketing strategy that reaches a large audience of consumers through physically printed material. Hard copy advertisements are published in a variety of media, including magazines, newspapers, brochures, and direct mail (Hafez, M., 2021). Additionally, when it comes to drawing in customers, print materials like brochures and booklets are more or less successful than electronic ones like mail and online ads. Dayton, K. (2016). Additionally, the location or setting in which an advertisement appears is referred to as the advertising context. When it comes to print advertisements, context can include news pieces, editorial content, and advertisements for unrelated or connected products.

Hence, it is crucial that the advertiser considers the importance of context and design while placing the advertisement to ensure that there is no possibility of misunderstanding. The purpose of the paper is to determine how context can affect how an accompanying advertisement is interpreted and how it might be leveraged to the advantage of the advertisement to guarantee that the intended outcome is obtained. As a result, even though people's lives are becoming more and more digital, print media remains a crucial component of the marketing mix (Usmani, A. K., & Alam, A., 2015). Businesses can increase their exposure, contact new clients, and run campaigns that engage their target audiences by investing in print media.

Several studies proved that each dimension of Social Media Marketing Strategy and Print Media Strategy required either marketing operation excellence or increased customer satisfaction as a mediator variable effect on marketing performance (Chanthinok, K., Ussahawanitchakit, P., & Jhundra-Indra, P., 2015). Further, research shows that social media marketing needs to have the indicators such as persuasion, accessibility and self-involvement, to provide accurate information to the clientele. Moreover, social media platforms can provide the institution with the opportunity to directly engage with prospective students and the broader community through interactive and visually appealing content. This may include showcasing campus facilities, student projects and special events highlighting the active campus life and innovative educational programs available.

While print media marketing needs to have to indicators such as persuasion, attraction and self-involvement. Additional, print media advertising, although more traditional, often offers tangible opportunities to reach prospective students and their families. This can be especially effective in local communities where printed materials such as tarpaulins and flyers can be distributed at strategic locations. Print advertising can complement social media efforts by providing a physical reminder of the business brand and its services. By integrating print and social media advertising strategies, businesses are able to create a comprehensive marketing campaign that effectively communicates its unique selling proposition to a wide audience. This approach not only raises awareness of the business but also showcases the organization as a forward-thinking, community-engaged learning center.

Hence, the researchers would like to assess the Level of Effectiveness of Print Media and Social Media Advertisement used by Cagayan Valley Computer and Information Technology College, Inc. (CVCITC).

Statement of the Problem:

This study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of effectiveness on the use of print media initiatives of CVCITC in terms of:
 - a. Persuasion;
 - b. Attraction; and
 - c. Self-involvement?
2. What is the level of effectiveness on the use of social media advertisements of CVCITC in terms of:
 - a. Persuasion;
 - b. Acceptability; and
 - c. Self-involvement?
3. Is there a significant difference between the level of effectiveness on the use of print media initiatives to the level of effectiveness on the use of social media advertisements of CVCITC?

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference on the use of print media initiatives to the level of effectiveness on the use of social media advertisement of CVCITC.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed the quantitative-correlational research method. The researchers used a survey method of research to identify the Effectiveness of Print vs. Social Media Advertisement as a Marketing Strategy of Cagayan Valley Computer and Information Technology College (CVCITC), Inc. Senior High School, Santiago City, Philippines. This study determined the level of effectiveness on the use of Print and Social Media Advertisement of CVCITC. The study was done from October 2023 to April 2024. Using Slovin's formula with 5% margin of error, there were two hundred forty-nine (249) respondents agreed to participate in this study. The respondents are determined using stratified random sampling. The researchers' utilized survey questionnaire. The said instrument

underwent validation and was subjected to an item analysis procedure. The statistical treatment used were frequency weighted mean, and t-test of relationship.

The researchers utilized a Likert scale in interpreting the survey questionnaire result.

Table 1. 4-point Likert Scale

Scale	Mean range	Descriptive Interpretation
4	3.26 – 4.00	Strongly Agree
3	2.51 – 3.25	Agree
2	1.75 – 2.50	Disagree
1	1.00 – 1.74	Strongly Disagree

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This part represents the results founds the needed answer to the research questions. The purpose of this part is to use the data collected on the print vs. social media advertisement: its effectiveness as marketing strategy of CVCITC.

PART I. The Level of Effectiveness on the Use of Print Media Initiatives of CVCITC

Table 2. Perception of the Senior High School students of CVCITC in the Level of Effectiveness on the Use of Print Media Initiatives in terms of Persuasion with its Corresponding Mean and Descriptive Interpretation.

Persuasion	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. It gives awareness about the quality education that CVCITC has to offer	3.30	STRONGLY AGREE
2. It contains the relevant information that I want to see	3.22	AGREE
3. It makes me believe that the skills of the students in this institution are being honed dynamically	3.14	AGREE
4. It makes me believe that learning is fun in CVCITC	3.14	AGREE
5. It persuades me to graduate from this institution	3.20	AGREE
Grand Mean	3.20	AGREE

Table 2 shows the perception of the Senior High School students of CVCITC in the Level of effectiveness on the use of print media initiatives in terms of persuasion with its corresponding mean and descriptive interpretation. The result reveals that the respondents are generally agree with the print advertisement in terms of persuasion as perceived by the students, since the general weighted mean is 3.20 with a descriptive interpretation of “Agree”. More so, the indicator “It gives awareness about the quality education that CVCITC has to offer”, gained the highest of 3.30 with descriptive interpretation of “Strongly Agree”. While the indicators “It makes me believe that the skills of the students in this institution are being honed dynamically” and “It makes me believe that learning is fun in the CVCITC”, gained the

lowest mean of 3.14, with a descriptive interpretation of “Agree”.

Persuasion effects in light of consumers’ cultural and individual dispositional characteristics when processing visually relational information. Of particular interest are the culturally driven self-views and individuals’ cognitive thinking styles. An experimental study involving visual metaphor manipulations in the context of print advertising was conducted. Their results showed that, visual metaphor techniques significantly enhanced the persuasion outcomes through consumers’ evaluation of the advertising message and the brand (Myers, J., & Jung, J. M., 2019).

Table 3. Perception of the Senior High School students of CVCITC in the Level of Effectiveness on the Use of Print Media Initiatives in terms of Attraction with its Corresponding Mean and Descriptive Interpretation.

Attraction	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. The design is appealing	3.16	AGREE
2. The fonts used are suitable to the theme	3.14	AGREE
3. The colors are satisfying to the eyes	3.17	AGREE
4. The elements (words/phrases) create good impact	3.24	AGREE
5. The advertisement gives accurate statement	3.07	AGREE
6. The advertisement is decent and worth reading for	3.18	AGREE
Grand Mean	3.16	AGREE

Table 3 shows the perception of the Senior High School students of CVCITC in the level of effectiveness on the use of print media initiatives in terms of attraction with its corresponding mean and descriptive interpretation. The result reveals that the respondents are generally agree with the print advertisement in terms of attraction as perceived by the students, since the general weighted mean is 3.16 with a descriptive interpretation of “Agree”. More so, the indicator “The elements (words/phrases) create good impact” gained the highest mean of 3.24 with its descriptive interpretation of “Agree”. While the indicator “The advertisement gives accurate statement” gained the lowest mean of 3.07 with the descriptive interpretation of “Agree”.

A structural latent variable model of apple variety demand is used to analyze the effect of variety specific newspaper advertisement characteristic n variety attraction (preferences), and in turn on variety demand (McLaren, S. et al., 2013).

Table 4. Perception of the Senior High School students of CVCITC in the Level of Effectiveness on the Use of Print Media Initiatives in terms of Self-Involvement with its Corresponding Mean and Descriptive Interpretation.

Self-Involvement	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. It convinces me that CVCITC is the perfect school for me	2.97	AGREE

2. It showcases the best features of the institution which I am looking for	2.97	AGREE
3. It makes me believe that CVCITC produces globally competent professionals	3.07	AGREE
4. It assures me that CVCITC vision and mission is attainable	3.20	AGREE
5. It makes me want to be part of CVCITC community	3.14	AGREE
Grand Mean	3.07	AGREE

Table 4 shows the perception of the Senior High School students of CVCITC in the level of effectiveness on the use of print media initiatives in terms of self-involvement with its corresponding mean and descriptive interpretation. The result reveals that the respondents are generally agreed with the print advertisement in terms of self-involvement as perceived by the students, since the general weighted mean is 3.07 with a descriptive interpretation of “Agree”. More so, the indicator “It assures me that CVCITC vision and mission is attainable” gained the highest mean of 3.20 with a descriptive interpretation of “Agree”. However, the indicators “It convinces me that CVCITC is the perfect school for me” and “It showcases the best features of the institution which I am looking for” gained the lowest mean of 2.97 with its descriptive interpretation of “Agree”.

There is less than full agreement in the advertising research community over the relationship between involvement and advertising effectiveness (Sun, S., Wojdyski, B., Binford, M. T., & Ramachandran, C., 2022).

PART II. The Level of Effectiveness on the Use of Social Media Initiatives of CVCITC

Table 5. Perception of the Senior High School students of CVCITC in the Level of Effectiveness on the Use of Social Media Advertisements in terms of Persuasion with its Corresponding Mean and Descriptive Interpretation.

Persuasion	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. It gives awareness about the quality education that CVCITC has to offer	3.27	STRONGLY AGREE
2. It contains the relevant information that I want to see	3.19	AGREE
3. It makes me believe that the skills of the students in this institution are being honed dynamically	3.10	AGREE
4. It makes me believe that learning is fun in CVCITC	3.16	AGREE
5. It persuades me to graduate from this institution	3.15	AGREE
Grand Mean	3.17	AGREE

Table 5 shows the perception of the Senior High School students of CVCITC in the level of effectiveness on the use of social media advertisements in terms of persuasion with its corresponding mean and descriptive interpretation. The result reveals that the respondents are generally agreed with the social media advertisement in terms of persuasion as perceived by the students, since the general weighted mean is 3.17 with a descriptive interpretation of “Agree”. More so, the indicator “It gives awareness about the quality education that CVCITC has to offer” gained the highest mean of 3.27 with its descriptive interpretation of “Strongly

Agree”. However, the indicator “It makes me believe that the skills of the students in this institution are being honed dynamically” gained the lowest mean of 3.10 with its descriptive interpretation of “Agree”.

Students are introduced to the practice of social influence in an array of contexts (e.g., advertising, marketing, politics, interpersonal relationships, social media, groups) and across a variety of topics (e.g., credibility, personality, deception, motivational appeals, visual persuasion). The new edition features expanded treatment of digital and social media; up-to-date research on theory and practice; an increased number of international cases; and new and expanded discussions of topics such as online influencers, disinformation and 'fake news,' deepfakes, message framing, normative influence, stigmatized language, and inoculation theory (Gass, R. H., & Seiter, J. S., 2022).

Table 6. Perception of the Senior High School students of CVCITC in the Level of Effectiveness on the Use of Social Media Advertisements in terms of Acceptability with its Corresponding Mean and Descriptive Interpretation.

Acceptability	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. The content is not offensive.	3.22	AGREE
2. The content gives reliable information.	3.22	AGREE
3. The advertisement creates good impact.	3.22	AGREE
4. The advertisement gives accurate statements.	3.16	AGREE
5. The advertisement is decent and worth reading for.	3.19	AGREE
Grand Mean	3.20	AGREE

Table 6 shows the perception of the Senior High School students of CVCITC in the level of effectiveness on the use of social media advertisements in terms of acceptability with its corresponding mean and descriptive interpretation. The result reveals that the respondents are generally agreed with the social media advertisement in terms of acceptability as perceived by the students, since the general weighted mean is 3.20 with a descriptive interpretation of “Agree”. More so, the indicators “The content is not offensive.”, “The content gives reliable information.”, and “The advertisement creates good impact.” gained the highest mean of 3.22 with descriptive interpretation of “Agree”. However, the indicator “The advertisement gives accurate statements.” gained the lowest mean of 3.16 with its descriptive interpretation of “Agree”.

The use of the internet and social media have changed consumer behavior and the ways in which companies conduct their business. Social and digital marketing offers significant opportunities to organizations through lower costs, improved brand awareness and increased sales. However, significant challenges exist from negative electronic word-of-mouth as well as intrusive and irritating online brand presence. This brings together the collective insight from several leading experts on issues relating to digital and social media marketing (Sharma, A., Dwivedi, Y. K., Arya, V., & Siddiqui, M. Q., 2021).

Table 7. Perception of the Senior High School students of CVCITC in the Level of

Effectiveness on the Use of Social Media Advertisements in terms of Self-Involvement with its Corresponding Mean and Descriptive Interpretation.

Self-Involvement	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. It convinces me that CVCITC is the perfect school for me.	3.04	AGREE
2. It showcases the best features of the institution which I am looking for.	3.10	AGREE
3. It makes me believe that CVCITC produces globally competent professionals.	3.13	AGREE
4. It assures me that CVCITC vision and mission is attainable	3.16	AGREE
5. It makes me want to be part of CVCITC community.	3.19	AGREE
Grand Mean	3.12	AGREE

Table 7 shows the perception of the Senior High School students of CVCITC in the level of effectiveness on the use of social media advertisements in terms of self-involvement with its corresponding mean and descriptive interpretation. The results reveals that the respondents generally agreed with the social media advertisement in terms of self-involvement as perceived by the students, since the general weighted mean is 3.12 with a descriptive interpretation of “Agree”. More so, the indicator “It makes me want to be part of CVCITC community.” gained the highest mean of 3.19 with the descriptive interpretation of “Agree”. However, the indicator “It convinces me that CVCITC is the perfect school for me.” gained the lowest mean of 3.04 with its descriptive interpretation of “Agree”.

As per analytic information of year 2018, there are 3190 million population, who comprise of 42 percent of total population, are using social media as a communication tool. The main objective of this research was to examine the influence of promoting content on a social media platform with reference to social media users. Another objective was to analyze the comparative outcome of information provided by a marketer on a social media platform for securing the attention of its users. Social media is attracting many people for searching and communicating with each other (Veer, N., Pawar, P., & Kolte, A., 2019).

PART III. The Significant Difference Result between the Level of Effectiveness on the Use of Print Media and Social Media Advertisement

Table 8. Significant Difference Result on the Level of Effectiveness on the Use of Print Media and Social Media Advertisement in terms of Persuasion

Use of Print Media	Use of social media	T Value	Sig .(2 Tailed)
Persuasion	<i>Persuasion</i>	0.975	0.330
	<i>Acceptability</i>	-0.057	0.955
	<i>Self-Involvement</i>	2.672**	0.008

Table 8 revealed that there's is no significant difference between the level of effectiveness on the use of print media in terms of persuasion and the level of effectiveness on the use of social media, between self-involvement its leads to rejection of hypothesis.

Table 9. Significant Difference Result on the Level of Effectiveness on the Use of Print Media and Social Media Advertisement in terms of Attraction

Use of Print Media	Use of social media	T Value	Sig .(2 Tailed)
Attraction	<i>Persuasion</i>	-0.644	0.520
	<i>Acceptability</i>	-1851	0.065
	<i>Self-Involvement</i>	1.083	0.280

Table 9 revealed that there's no significance difference between the level of effectiveness on the use of print media in terms of attraction and the level of effectiveness on the use of social media, its leads to acceptance of the hypothesis.

Table 10. Significant Difference Result on the Level of Effectiveness on the Use of Print Media and Social Media Advertisement in terms of Self-Involvement.

Use of Print Media	Use of social media	T Value	Sig .(2 Tailed)
Self-Involvement	<i>Persuasion</i>	-0.644	0.520
	<i>Acceptability</i>	-1851	0.065
	<i>Self-Involvement</i>	1.083	0.280

Table 10 revealed that there's no significance difference between the level of effectiveness on the use of print media in terms of self-involvement and the level of effectiveness on the use of social media, between persuasion and acceptability its leads to the rejection of hypothesis.

CONCLUSION

The following are the conclusions for the study that are based on the previously presented findings and their implications.

1. In terms of the level of effectiveness on the use of print initiatives of CVCITC respondents agreed on persuasion, attraction and self-involvement.
2. In terms of the level of effectiveness on the use of social media advertisement of CVCITC respondents strongly agreed on persuasion and agreed on acceptability and self-involvement.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the data gathered and the conclusion drawn from the study conducted, the researchers would like to recommend the following;

1. For the benefit of the school, social media advertising should deploy visual content

using high-quality images and videos to showcase school facilities, classrooms, extracurricular activities, and student life. Visual content is more engaging and can attract the attention of students and potential parents. Also Highlight academic achievements, athletic victories, community service projects, and any other notable accomplishments that demonstrate the school's excellence.

2. For the benefit of school, It is necessary to improve the use of print advertisement for CVCITC marketing strategy. Like flyers, Tarpaulins and others related to print advertisement. Visuals play a significant role in print ads. Use high-quality images that reflect the school's environment, students engaged in activities, or happy faces to evoke positive emotions. It is also to help students for choosing what is related to their studies.
3. For the students, it is necessary to enhance their skills when it comes to social media advertisement whether video presentation, or pictures are much better in CVCITC marketing strategy. And also, to boost their knowledge of social media advertisement because this will help in their studies.
4. For Teachers "Print Advertising vs. Social Media Advertising: Its Effectiveness as a CVCITC Marketing Strategy" will provide valuable information on comparative impact of traditional print advertising and social media marketing for school promotion. Conducting a comprehensive study to analyze factors such as reach, engagement, profitability and overall effectiveness will provide a data-driven approach to understanding which advertising mediums deliver results for the school.

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ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The researchers made sure that the conduct of the study followed ethical standards. The signing of an informed consent form with the Study participants was conducted before the data collection. The security of the privacy of research participants and the data provided was protected, securing an adequate level of anonymity and confidentiality. Moreover, this Study underwent rigorous review by the Ethics Review Committee and Research Panelist of Cagayan Valley Computer and Information Technology College, Inc. Senior High School Department to ensure it passed thru ethical standards. A Language editor also validated, checked, and reviewed the entire manuscript.

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